

Evaluating the Indigenous Plant Wealth of Government College for Women, Udhampur, J & K (UT) India

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Abstract

The Government College for Women campus supports a total of 108 medicinal trees representing diverse species with already reported significant therapeutic value. The tree population exhibited an uneven species distribution, with *Terminalia arjuna* (Arjun) emerging as the dominant species, comprising 30 individuals (27.78%). This species is widely valued for its bark, which is used in the treatment of cardiovascular disorders such as heart diseases, hypertension, and heart failure. The second most abundant species was *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun) with 15 trees (13.89%), known for its medicinal applications in managing diabetes, liver disorders, constipation, and other ailments. *Bauhinia variegata* and *Morus alba* were equally represented, each contributing 13 trees (12.04%), and are recognized for their anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties.

Moderate representation was observed for *Dalbergia sissoo* (Shisham) with 6 trees (5.56%), used in treating skin diseases, digestive disorders, and wound healing, and *Cinnamomum camphor* with 4 trees (3.70%), valued for its antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory effects. *Ficus religiosa* and *Grewia tiliifolia* each accounted for 2.78% of the population. Several medicinally important species, including *Mangifera indica*, *Melia azedarach*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Punica granatum*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Ricinus communis*, *Mallotus philippensis*, and *Albizia lebbbeck*, were sparsely distributed (1.85%), yet possess a wide range of medicinal properties such as antioxidant, antidiabetic, antimicrobial, hepatoprotective, and detoxifying effects. *Acacia catechu* was the least represented species (0.93%), known for its astringent, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties.

Overall, the four most dominant species—*Terminalia arjuna*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Bauhinia variegata*, and *Morus alba*—together constituted approximately 65.74% of the total tree population. The Shannon–Wiener diversity index ($H' = 2.40$) indicated moderate species diversity, while the Simpson's diversity index ($1 - D = 0.87$) suggested high diversity with low dominance. These findings reflect relatively stable ecological conditions and highlight the campus as a valuable repository of medicinal plant diversity with considerable therapeutic potential.

Keywords

Medicinal Trees, College For Womens, Udhampur, Campus Biodiversity.

Introduction

Plants play a fundamental role in maintaining ecological stability and supporting human well-being. In addition to providing shade and contributing to a healthy environment, many plant species possess significant medicinal properties and have been integral to traditional systems of medicine such as **Ayurveda, Unani, and folk medicine** since ancient times. India is recognized as one of the world's major centers of medicinal plant diversity and depends heavily on botanical resources for primary healthcare as well as for the preparation of herbal medicines (Ved & Goraya, 2007). The growing demand for plant-based remedies has further emphasized the need to **document, conserve, and promote the sustainable utilization of medicinal flora**.

Objective of study

The objective of the present study was to document and identify the medicinal tree species present on the Government College for Women campus and to analyze their species composition, abundance, and distribution. The study also aimed to evaluate the diversity of medicinal trees using ecological indices such as the Shannon–Wiener and Simpson's diversity indices. In addition, it sought to highlight the medicinal and therapeutic importance of the recorded species and to assess the ecological status and stability of the campus vegetation based on patterns of species dominance and diversity.

Review of Literature

Educational institutions, particularly college and university campuses, are increasingly acknowledged as important repositories of plant biodiversity. These

green spaces often support a wide variety of plant species under relatively undisturbed conditions, making them ideal locations for floristic surveys and conservation-oriented studies. Several investigations conducted across Indian academic institutions have reported considerable richness of medicinal plant species on campuses and highlighted their importance in environmental education, biodiversity conservation, and scientific research (Khare, P. B. and Shukla, A. N. 2005;Sahu, P. K., and Dhal, N. K. 2011.; Manhas et.al., 2014; Bhellim B. L 2014;Humaira, S et.al.,. 2020; Katoch, N. K., et al ., 2022.) Such studies emphasize that institutional landscapes serve not only as ecological assets but also as living laboratories for students and researchers.

Similar studies have been undertaken in various other regions of India as well as other country. A floristic assessment at the **University of Chittagong Campus, Bangladesh** was conducted by Momen, R *et al* 2006 and documented a diverse assemblage of medicinal tree species within plantation areas, underscoring the role of campus green spaces in preserving regional plant diversity . Likewise, Humaria *et al* (2020) studied the flora of Baba Gulam Badshah University Campus Rajouri J&K, reported substantial floristic richness and stressed the significance of academic campuses in promoting biodiversity awareness and conservation. Despite numerous studies conducted across India and neighboring regions, many academic campuses remain insufficiently explored, particularly with respect to their medicinal plant resources. **Government Degree College for Women, Udhampur**, located in a region characterized by diverse vegetation, represents one such understudied site. Documentation of medicinal plants within the campus is essential not only from a conservation perspective but also for their potential **educational, ecological, and economic value**. These plant species may serve as valuable resources for teaching and research and could also contribute to income generation through their utilization in Ayurvedic formulations and other herbal products.

The present study aims to **document and catalogue the medicinal plant species** occurring within the campus of Government Degree College for Women, Udhampur. By highlighting these species, the study seeks to promote their conservation, enhance botanical awareness among students, and provide a baseline for future **ethnobotanical and phytochemical investigations**.

Methodology

Study Area

The study was conducted at the Government College for Women, Udhampur, Jammu and Kashmir (UT), India in the period 2023-24. The college campus comprises plantation zones, open green spaces, and roadside vegetation. The area experiences a subtropical to temperate climate and supports diverse tree species, including several of medicinal importance. The relatively protected nature of the campus provides suitable conditions for floristic assessment.

Data Collection

During the study period, repeated field visits were made to ensure comprehensive coverage of all vegetation patches. All tree species with known medicinal value were recorded through direct observation, and the number of individuals of each species was enumerated. Only mature and healthy trees were included to ensure consistency in data collection. Plant species were identified using standard regional floras and taxonomic keys and with the help of researchers. Identification was cross-verified with published botanical literature. Scientific nomenclature was validated using accepted taxonomic databases to ensure accuracy and consistency.

Data Analysis

Species composition and abundance were analyzed quantitatively. The percentage composition of each species was calculated based on the total number of trees recorded. Species diversity was assessed using the Shannon–Wiener diversity index (H') (Shannon, C.E. and Weaver, W. (1949) and Simpson's diversity index ($1 - D$) (Simpson, E.H. 1949), following standard ecological methods.

Ethical Considerations

The study was non-destructive in nature. No plant specimens were collected, and all observations were made without causing disturbance to the existing vegetation

Result and Discussion

The Govt. College for Womens campus hosts 108 medicinal trees (table -2), with *Terminalia arjuna*(Arjun) being the most abundant, constituting 27.78% of the total trees and valued for its bark in treating heart diseases, hypertension, and heart failure (Dwivedi 2007). *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun) follows at 13.89%, used for

diabetes, liver disorders, constipation, and other ailments Murngarnandar et al 2001; Shanker et.,al. 2007). *Bauhinia variegata* and *Morus alba* each account for 12.04% of the trees, offering anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties (Mishra et., al. 2013). *Dalbergia sissoo* (Shisham) forms 5.56%, beneficial for skin diseases, digestive issues, and wound healing(Bhattacharya et.,al. 2014). Moderate representation includes *Cinnamomum camphor* (3.7%), *Ficus religiosa*, and *Grewia tiliifolia* (2.78% each), which contribute antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, and wound-healing effects(Chandraseker et.,al. 2010; Hamidpour et.,al. 2013; Kumar et al 2022). Several species such as *Mangifera indica*, *Melia azedarach*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Punica granatum*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Ricinus communis*, *Mallotus philippensis*, and *Albizia lebbek* are less abundant (1.85%), yet their medicinal properties range from antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial to antidiabetic, liver-protective, and detoxifying effects(Bhowmik et al, 2009; 2010; Biswas et al. 2010; Baliga et.al 2011; Jasuja et.al 2012; Sen and Batra 2012; Gangwar et. al 2014;Shaygannia et.,al. 2016; Hasan, et al 2016; Marwat et al 2017; Alsayar and Wahab 2021; Balkrishna et.,al. 2022). *Acacia catechu* is the least represented (0.93%), valued for its astringent, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties(Danish and Alam 2024). Overall, the campus demonstrates a rich diversity of medicinal plants, both in terms of species variety and therapeutic potential(table-1, bar chart).

The tree population showed an uneven distribution among species. *Terminalia arjuna* was the most dominant species with 30 individuals (27.78%), followed by *Syzygium cumini*(15 trees; 13.89%),*Bauhinia variegata*(13 trees;12.04%), and *Morus alba*(13 trees; 12.04%). These four species together constituted approximately 65.74% of the total tree population. Moderate representation was observed in *Dalbergia sissoo*(6 trees; 5.56%) and *Cinnamomum camphor*(4 trees; 3.70%), while several species such as *Mangifera indica*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Punica granatum*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Ricinus communis*, *Mallotus philippensis*, and *Albizia lebbek* were represented by only one or two individuals. The Shannon–Wiener diversity index ($H' = 2.40$) indicated moderate species diversity, whereas the Simpson's diversity index ($1 - D = 0.87$) reflected high diversity with low dominance, suggesting relatively stable ecological conditions within the study area.

Discussion

The Government College for Women's campus , Udampur supports a rich assemblage of 108 medicinal trees, exhibiting both ecological diversity and therapeutic significance due to their varied bioactive properties. Among these, *Terminalia arjuna* is the most abundant species, constituting 30 individuals (27.78%), and is extensively valued in traditional and modern medicinal systems for its cardioprotective, antihypertensive, lipid-lowering, antioxidant, and anti-inflammatory effects, primarily attributed to its bark rich in glycosides, flavonoids, tannins, and triterpenoids, making it effective in managing heart disease, hypertension, and heart failure (Naji et al., 2025). *Syzygium cumini* (Jamun), forming 13.89% of the trees, has long been used to manage diabetes mellitus, improve liver function, and aid digestive disorders, with scientific studies validating its potential to regulate blood glucose levels, reduce oxidative stress, and provide hepatoprotective benefits through its flavonoids and phenolic compounds (Ayyanar and Subash-Babu, 2012; Chagas et al., 2015). Both *Bauhinia variegata* and *Morus alba* (each 12.04%) are recognized for anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antioxidant, and antimicrobial properties; *Bauhinia variegata* traditionally addresses inflammation and metabolic imbalance, while *Morus alba* components such as flavonoids and phenolics contribute to glucose regulation and microbial inhibition .(*Dalbergia sissoo* (Shisham, 5.56%) possesses medicinal relevance for skin diseases, digestive issues, and wound healing due to its bioactive phytochemicals, and *Cinnamomum camphor* (Camphor tree, 3.7%) is known for antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic effects. *Ficus religiosa* and *Grewia tiliifolia* (each 2.78%) add to the therapeutic diversity with antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, and wound-healing activities. Additionally, several species present in lower abundance (each ~1.85%), including *Mangifera indica*, *Melia azedarach*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Punica granatum*, *Phyllanthus emblica*, *Ziziphus mauritiana*, *Ricinus communis*, *Mallotus philippensis*, and *Albizia lebbek*, are documented to possess medicinal properties ranging from antioxidant and anti-inflammatory to antidiabetic, hepatoprotective, antimicrobial, and detoxifying effects (Subedi et al., 2022). *Acacia catechu*, though least represented (0.93%), remains significant due to its astringent, antimicrobial, and wound-healing properties. Collectively, this assemblage demonstrates moderate species diversity (Shannon–Wiener index $H' = 2.40$) and high overall diversity with low dominance (Simpson's index $1 - D = 0.87$),

suggesting a stable ecological community that supports both dominant medicinal species and a wider reservoir of therapeutic plants, underscoring the campus's value as a living repository of ethnobotanical and pharmacological resources.

Table1. List of medicinal plant species of the Govt. College for Women, Udhampur

S.N.	Plant Species	Number of trees	Family	English Name	Common Name	Part Used	Medicinal Properties
1.	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>		Combretaceae	Arjun Tree	Arjuna	Bark	Ischaemic heart disease, Hypertension, Mitral regurgitationendothelial dysfunctionheart failure
2.	<i>Mangifera indica</i>		Anacardiaceae	Mango Tree	Aam	Fruits, Roots, bark, leaves	Anti-oxidant, Anti-diabetic, Anti-viral, Anti-helminthic Anti-inflammatory
3.	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)		Myrtaceae	Jambolan	Jamun	bark, leaves, fruit seeds	Treat leucorrhoea, stomachache, fever, dermopathy constipation, inhibit blood discharges in the faeces reduce radiation-induced DNA damage. Antidiabetic, enlargement of the spleen, and chronic diarrhea. remedy for bleeding piles and correcting liver disorders.
4.	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.		Meliaceae	China tree	Bakan or Dreka	Whole plant	Rheumatic pain, loss of appetite, stomachache, Asthma , Used for gonorrhoea, to treat malaria and to expel parasitic worms diabetes, cure pimples, blood purifier malaria fever and leprosy
5.	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> Correa		Rutaceae	Bael	Bilwa/Sriphal	Whole plant	Chronic diarrhea, dysentery, peptic ulcers, laxative for astringency, and respiratory ailments, Anti-inflammatory Anticancer Antidiabetic Activity Antimicrobial Activity
6.	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>		Meliaceae	Margosa Tree	Neem	leaf, bark, root, seed, and flowers	Hepatoprotective Neuroprotective, Cardio protective Immunomodulatory, Wound healing
7.	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.		Punicaceae	pomegranate	Anar	Fruit	Treat tapeworm parasites, Diabetes by Indians, Antioxidant, Antiinflammatory, antibacterial, antimicrobial, and antifungal properties
8.	<i>Emblica officinalis</i>		Euphorbiaceae	Indian gooseberry	Amla	Dried fruits, Fresh fruit, seed, leaves root bark flowers	Diabetes Heart diseases, Immunomodulatory activity Antipyretic and Analgesic Activities, Snake Venom Neutralizer
9.	<i>Acacia catechu</i>		Mimosaceae	Gum Arabic Tree	khar	Heartwood, bark, and leaves.	Astringent & Antimicrobial, Anti-inflammatory & Antioxidant, Wound Healing & Antiseptic, Used for relieving diarrhea, externally for managing wounds and fungal infections.
10.	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>		Moraceae	Sacred Fig, Bodhi Tree	Peepal	bark, leaves, roots, fruits, seeds, and latex	for treating diabetes, wounds, anxiety, respiratory issues (asthma, coughs), and digestive problems, thanks to compounds like tannins, flavonoids, and phenolics, offering anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, and antimicrobial benefits.
11.	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>		Rhamnaceae	(Indian jujube,	Ber	fruit, leaves and seeds	antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antibacterial effects, fever, skin problems, digestive ailments (diarrhea, constipation), and potentially supporting heart and metabolic health.

12	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i>		Malvaceae	Common Indian Linden.	Dhamin,	fruit, bark, root, leaves, and buds	Anti-inflammatory and Antioxidan, Antidiabetic, Antimicrobial, Gastrointestinal Health, Wound Healing
13	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>		Fabaceae	Indian Rosewood	Shisham, tali	leaves; bark; wood and roots	for skin diseases (leukoderma, scabies), digestive issues (diarrhea, ulcers), fever, pain, syphilis, and wound healing, with extracts showing anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antimicrobial, neuroprotective, and bone-healing properties
14	<i>Bauhinia varigata</i>		Caesalpinioideae	Orchid Tree	Kachnar	leaves, flowers, buds, bark, roots, and seeds	For its anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, antioxidant, and anti-tumor properties
16	<i>Ricinus communis,</i>		Euphorbiaceae	Caster	Arandi	seeds, leaves roots and bark	Anti-inflammatory, Skin and Hair Care, Wound Healing
17	<i>Cinnamomum camphor</i>		Lauraceae	camphorwood	Karpura	wood, leaves, and roots	Antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and analgesic properties.
18	<i>Morus alba</i>		Moraceae	White Mulberry,	Mulberry, shahtoot	leaves, twigs, root bark, and fruits	Anti-diabetic, Antioxidant & Anti-inflammatory, Antimicrobial, Liver protection, diuretic, improves eyesight, hair health,
19	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i> (Lam.) Muell. Arg		Euphorbiaceae	Spurge	Kamala tree, Kumkum tree	Fruits	Anthelmintic (Anti-worm), Dermatological Aid: Anti-inflammatory, Antibacterial and Antifungal: Digestive Health, Antioxidant
20	<i>Albizia lebbek</i> (L.) Benth.		Fabaceae	Shirish/ Woman's Tongue tree	Lebbek Tree	bark, leaves, flowers, roots and seed	Excellent for asthma, bronchitis, coughs, Anti-Poison/Detox, Skin & Wounds, anti-diabetic, treats night blindness, earaches, toothache, and paralysis.

Table-2: Percentage Composition of Tree Species

S.No.	Plant Species	Number of Trees	Percentage (%)
1	<i>Terminalia arjuna</i>	30	27.78
2	<i>Mangifera indica</i>	2	1.85
3	<i>Syzygium cumini</i> (L.)	15	13.89
4	<i>Melia azedarach</i> L.	2	1.85
5	<i>Aegle marmelos</i> Correa	2	1.85
6	<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	2	1.85
7	<i>Punica granatum</i> L.	2	1.85
8	<i>Phyllanthus emblica</i>	2	1.85
9	<i>Acacia catechu</i>	1	0.93
10	<i>Ficus religiosa</i>	3	2.78
11	<i>Ziziphus mauritiana</i>	2	1.85
12	<i>Grewia tiliifolia</i>	3	2.78
13	<i>Dalbergia sissoo</i>	6	5.56
14	<i>Bauhinia variegata</i>	13	12.04
15	<i>Ricinus communis</i>	2	1.85
16	<i>Cinnamomum camphor</i>	4	3.7
17	<i>Morus alba</i>	13	12.04
18	<i>Mallotus philippensis</i>	2	1.85
19	<i>Albizia lebbeck</i>	2	1.85
Total		108	100

Shannon–Wiener Diversity Index (H'): 2.40; Simpson's Diversity Index (1 – D): 0.87

Conclusion

The medicinal tree population on the Government College for Women's campus demonstrates a rich diversity of species with significant therapeutic potential, reflecting both ecological stability and ethnobotanical importance. The dominance of *Terminalia arjuna*, *Syzygium cumini*, *Bauhinia variegata*, and *Morus alba* highlights the preferential planting or favorable growth conditions for species with high medicinal value, while the presence of moderately represented and rare species such as *Dalbergia sissoo*, *Aegle marmelos*, *Azadirachta indica*, and *Acacia catechu* underscores the campus's role as a repository of less common yet pharmaceutically valuable plants. Diversity indices indicate a moderate to high species diversity with low dominance, suggesting that the ecosystem is stable and capable of supporting a wide range of medicinal plants. The coexistence of dominant and rare species not only enhances ecological balance but also provides opportunities for conservation, research, and sustainable utilization of medicinal resources. Overall, the campus serves as a living laboratory and a valuable resource for education, conservation, and pharmacological studies, emphasizing the importance of maintaining and expanding this green and medicinal heritage.

Significance of the Work

The present study holds substantial ecological, ethnobotanical, educational, and conservation significance. By documenting the diversity, abundance, and medicinal properties of 108 tree species, the research provides a comprehensive baseline for understanding the therapeutic potential and ecological value of campus vegetation. The dominance of highly valued medicinal species such as *Terminalia arjuna* and *Syzygium cumini* highlights their importance in traditional and modern healthcare, while the presence of less abundant species like *Aegle marmelos*, *Acacia catechu*, and *Phyllanthus emblica* emphasizes the need for conservation of rare and pharmacologically important trees.

From an ecological perspective, the study demonstrates the stability and diversity of the campus ecosystem, as reflected by the Shannon–Wiener and Simpson's diversity indices, suggesting that the area can sustain both common and rare medicinal species. Ethnobotanically, the research serves as a valuable reference for understanding how local flora contributes to traditional medicine, nutrition, and overall human health, potentially guiding future pharmacological studies.

The work also holds educational and awareness value, providing students and staff with knowledge about the medicinal, ecological, and cultural importance of the campus flora, which can promote sustainable planting, conservation initiatives, and responsible utilization of plant resources. Finally, the study establishes a foundation for future research, including detailed phytochemical analyses, cultivation strategies, and the development of herbal remedies,

contributing to the preservation of biodiversity and traditional knowledge in an urban educational setting.

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